

Nonlocality and Time-Space Decoupling in Quantum Mechanics

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In a previous note (1), we argued that one may write velocity $v=x/t$ in both the relativistic and nonrelativistic free particle classical action expressions and vary x and t independently to find: d/dt Action = $-E$ and d/dx Action = p . From this, one may create $\exp(i$ Action) which satisfies the Schrodinger equation for a free particle. Quantum mechanics, however, is also considered to be a statistical theory unlike deterministic classical mechanics. In this note we argue that the decoupling of time and space is the signature of a statistical equilibrium and that this has important consequences. In fact, we argue it leads to a periodic function for the probability of momentum in space. A periodic function, however, does not conserve probability at each x point and so one is forced to extend to two dimensions i.e. introduce a complex probability. Similar arguments hold for the average potential $V(x)$. It may be broken into impulses, but these may not be linked to x in any preferential way that would create deterministic motion in an equilibrium. As a result, one obtains periodic type functions which are nonlocal and this leads to the idea of orthonormal basis functions as argued in (2).

Classical Action of a Free Particle and Decoupling Space and Time

As shown in (1), if one writes the classical action for a free relativistic or nonrelativistic particle i.e.

$$\text{Action} = T (-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}) \quad \text{where } c=1 \quad \text{or} \quad \text{Action} = T .5m_0 vv \quad ((1))$$

one may use $v=x/t$ and vary x and t independently, decoupling space and time. This yields in both cases:

$$d\text{Action}/dt = -E \quad \text{and} \quad d\text{Action}/dx = p \quad ((2))$$

Using $\exp(i$ Action) one may obtain the free particle wavefunction which satisfies the Schrodinger equation for a free particle.

The question remains, however: Why should one decouple space and time as done above? We try to answer this in the next section.

Decoupling of Space-Time as Equivalent to Statistical Equilibrium

Classical mechanics is based on the idea of linking space and time i.e. on $x(t)$. This means that changes to x as a function of t (i.e. velocity and acceleration) are known at each $x(t)$ point. In other words, one follows the particle in space and time meaning there are distinct values of velocity and acceleration at different $x(t)$ as well distinct force values. Time is not removed from the system because one must follow the particle in time as well as space.

Equilibrium, even classical equilibrium, removes time from the picture i.e. one has a system which does not change in time. This means one may not follow a quantum particle in space-time. We argue that the implications are greater than this. Quantum mechanics uses $V(x)$ the potential which yields $F = -dV/dx$. F , however, describes exactly how a particle changes (accelerates) at each x point by Newton's second law. This then cannot be an equilibrium picture. To create an equilibrium scenario, one needs to break the force or potential into pieces which are invariant in space so as to not give any preference to any x point which would predict motion at this point. These pieces, however, must combine to yield $V(x)$ which is a function of x . It seems that the only way to accomplish this is to use a periodic function. Thus,

$$V(x) = \text{Sum } V(k,x) \quad ((2))$$

In the case of a quantum particle, it seems it may be characterized by momentum, but ((2)) shows this momentum receives hits periodically throughout space. Thus, it seems momentum probability should also be periodic throughout space, otherwise if a particular $P(\pi)$ has preferred positions, one could map the x axis to various preferred momentum values and recreate a kind of classical mechanical behaviour which contradicts ((2)). On average, however, kinetic energy at x plus potential should equal E , so probability of momentum must also contain x (as argued in previous notes). This again suggests a periodic probability.

Two Dimensional Probability of a Quantum Particle

In the previous section we argued that equilibrium requires a momentum probability periodic in space. This, however, would not conserve probability at each x point. As a result, it seems one needs to extend to two dimensions or introduce a complex probability (which is two dimensional) to bypass this problem.

It has not yet been argued that the periodic probability is $\exp(ipx)$. In previous notes we have shown that the pieces in ((2)) should yield an impulse hit i.e. $dV(k,x)/dx$ proportional to $kV(k,x)$ where $V(k,x)$ is like a probability. In such a case, $V(k,x) = V_k \exp(ikx)$ is a solution and the periodic functions become $\sin(px)$ and $\cos(px)$ i.e. $\exp(ipx)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the decoupling of space and time in the classical action when taking derivatives i.e. setting velocity $v=x/t$ and taking d/dx and d/dt independently is equivalent to statistical equilibrium in which there is no link between x and t . This is the opposite scenario of classical mechanics where the fundamental solution is $x(t)$. Quantum mechanics uses $V(x)$ which is directly linked to this deterministic idea through $F = -dV/dx$ at each x point. Thus, one must break $V(x)$ into pieces which are not preferential in x . The way to do this, it seems, is to introduce a periodic function in x i.e. $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k \ V(k,x)$. Insisting that $d/dx V(k,x)$ be proportional to $kV(k,x)$ yields $V_k \exp(ikx)$ as a solution. Similarly, the momentum probability of a quantum particle should not be preferential in x although it must contain x because one must compute average kinetic energy at x such that $KE(x) + V(x) = E$. The best solution again is a periodic one. We argue that it is the idea of equilibrium which drives this process of eliminating

any preferred x point. If there were any preferences, then the x axis could be mapped to preferred momentum values which is essentially the classical mechanical nonequilibrium approach. Choosing a periodic function for momentum probability i.e. $\sin(px)$, however, is problematic because probability is not conserved. One needs to extend to two dimensions to ensure that at least a modulus of probability is conserved i.e. use the complex probability $\exp(ipx)$.

Thus, we argue that the decoupling of space and time is equivalent to a statistical scenario in which there can be no preferential treatment in linking p momentum with x points. This ultimately leads to the periodic and complex particle probabilities of quantum mechanics.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Klein-Gordon equation, $\exp(i\text{Action})$ [Propagator] and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Quantum Mechanics and Orthonormal Basis Functions (preprint, zenodo, 2021)